

Sample Name: PVC <1 μm

Material: Polyvinyl Chloride

Size: <1 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 98% particles are <1 μm
- Particles have an irregular rounded morphology
- $3.2 \pm 0.8 \cdot 10^{12}$ particles per gram
- $15200 \pm 1520 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- Na, Zr, Ca, P, Si, Mg were the most abundant contaminant, ranging from 180-4000 $\mu\text{g/g}$
 - Ca, Zn and P are present in the stabilisers
 - Fe, Ni, Cr are present due to stainless steel
 - Zr and Y are present due to the milling beads
- Occasional Zr spots also observed with SEM-EDX in a small percentage of particles
- No changes due to milling observed in Raman spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_v : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_N : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D _v	D _N	N _w	A _w
8.87 ± 0.25	2.82 ± 0.36	0.59 ± 0.05	0.28 ± 0.01	5.72 ± 0.86	0.21 ± 0.01	3.2 ± 0.8 10 ¹²	15200 ± 1520

Morphology (using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) provided by TNO)

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Element	Concentration
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{Cl}$ (PVC)	99.27%
Na	3915 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Zr	1205 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Ca	816 $\mu\text{g/g}$
P	730 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Si	240 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Mg	179 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Fe	10 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Y	77 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Ni, Cu, Br, Zn, Ga, As	<5 $\mu\text{g/g}$

Raman Spectroscopy (provided by Wessling)